

Horizon Europe Project 101059188

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ABSTRACT

This proposal aims to understand, through the conceptual lens of home, tenants' and landlords' practices in 'hidden' private rental sectors, where informal transactions increase risks and hide vulnerability away from state regulatory gaze - as the Covid-19 pandemic has undoubtedly exposed across much of the globe. Taking the post-communist context as an example of an emerging and hidden PRS and drawing on a specific view of home as assemblage of materials, money, relations and affects, this research project aims to: **Understand** a hidden social world, by asking why tenants and landlords engage in the sector, whether their practices permit making a private tenancy home, and how they construct ideas of power, risk and trust; **Nuance** existing concepts of space and propose new concepts of time as they unfold in a privately rented home; **Inform** the national and international debate on PRS regulation. To achieve its aims, the proposal takes a qualitative multi-disciplinary approach, creating synergies between methods developed from meta-ethnography (critical interpretative synthesis), sociology and visual studies (qualitative questionnaires and photo-elicitation interviews), and public policy (scenario building). Through its focus on rental housing, a mechanism that generates important inequalities of wealth, health and wellbeing, the project aligns with the European Union strategy of creating a more resilient and inclusive society, and its concern for addressing inequalities.

CORDIS: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059188?isPreviewer=1>

WEBSITE: <https://unibuc.ro/cercetare/promovarea-rezultatelor-cercetarii/proiecte-de-cercetare/proiecte-cu-finantare-internationala/affective-prs/>

THIS DOCUMENT

In the spirit of collegiality and transparency, I've made my successful MSCA proposal (PART B-1, 10 pages) available as Open Access. I hope it serves as a helpful example for anyone considering submitting their own application. The proposal was submitted in October 2021 and received a score of 98.60% (if I recall correctly). Best of luck with your own proposal!

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1. EXCELLENCE

1.1 *Quality and pertinence of the project's research and innovation objectives*

In a nutshell: This proposal aims to understand, through the conceptual lens of home, tenants' and landlords' practices in 'hidden' private rental sectors (PRS), where informal transactions increase risks and hide vulnerability away from state regulatory gaze - as the Covid-19 pandemic has undoubtedly exposed across much of the globe. Taking the post-communist (PC) context as an example of an emerging and hidden PRS and drawing on a specific view of home as assemblage of materials, money, relations and affects (DeLanda 2016), this research project aims to: **Understand** a hidden social world, by asking why tenants and landlords engage in the sector, whether their practices permit making a private tenancy home, and how they construct ideas of power, risk and trust; **Nuance** existing concepts of space and propose new concepts of time as they unfold in a privately rented home; **Inform** the national and international debate on PRS regulation. To achieve its aims, the proposal takes a qualitative multi-disciplinary approach, creating synergies between methods developed from meta-ethnography (critical interpretative synthesis), sociology and visual studies (qualitative questionnaires and photo-elicitation interviews), and public policy (scenario building). Through its focus on rental housing, a mechanism that generates important inequalities of wealth, health and wellbeing, the project aligns with the European Union (EU) strategy of creating a more resilient and inclusive society, and its concern for addressing inequalities.

1.1.1 **Emerging PRS and their 'hidden' social worlds**

The 2008 Global Financial Crisis and the Covid-19 pandemic have exposed rental housing as a mechanism that generates important inequalities of wealth, health and wellbeing in much of the world (Soaita et al. 2020a), failing to give many tenants a 'home' (Soaita et al. 2020b). Academic interest in the Anglo-Saxon countries (AS-c) has recently contributed perturbing insights (e.g. housing precarity; insecure occupancy), raising legitimate concerns about tenants' wellbeing in more hidden, hence riskier PRS. Sharing these important concerns, this proposal engages with the affective economies of the hidden PRS, taking as a case-study the PC space, specifically Romania.

There are important reasons to engage with the PC geographies. Their PRS are still emerging as private rental housing was mostly banned until 1989/1992, making them an expression of the new social order and a laboratory for observing how new social norms are being formed. PC rental housing is almost totally left to the market, yet socially accepted informality, particularly in South-East Europe and the former USSR, places its social world out of sight, raising questions on how tenants and landlords negotiate power, risk and trust and whether a private tenancy becomes a tenant's home. Moreover, the very new research interest in PRS is uncomfortably dominated by Anglo-Saxon accounts (Soaita et al. 2020b): a systematic search in SCOPUS (17.09.2021) found 24,699 'housing' and 'home' publications, of which 57% focused on AS-c and 2% on the 29 countries of the former Eastern Bloc and the USSR. Narrowing down the same search to PRS, only 409 publications were found, demonstrating the novelty of this subject of study and its even higher Anglo-Saxon bias (78%) with only 17 publications studying some PC states, none covering Romania.

PC states are 'homeownership' societies (officially 80%-98% country rate) with owner-occupation supported by family resources and co-residence rather than mortgages, yet gradually more people rent privately, often informally (Hegedüs et al 2018). While we know who is renting privately and why in the AS-c market-based PRS (e.g. students, mobile professionals, low-income, migrants, those priced out of homeownership) and we start to understand their precarious experiences, similar questions have yet to be explored in PC space. Exceptionally, Hegedüs et al (2018) offered a comparative work on the private renting arrangements in PC states, but tenants' voices were not heard.

Landlords' experiences are even less documented than those of tenants, even in the AS-c. Quantitative research is emerging (e.g. Arundel 2017) but only exceptionally are landlords' voices documented (Bierre et al. 2009; Soaita et al. 2016). It was shown that large-portfolio landlords take a business outlook whereas for those owning one or few properties, the PRS economy takes a more affective turn for a range of reasons. For instance, the rented property was a family home, is earmarked as a child's future home, is an indispensable income/pension supplement, or is the only family safety-net. In the emerging PRS of the PC states, the tenant/landlord relationship may display an even more affective register than in the mature ones of the AS-c because housing is commonly seen as a home not as an asset (Soaita 2015) - with unknown implications for the welfare and wellbeing of those involved.

1.1.2 **Theoretical ambition: conceptualising home as assemblage**

'Home' is a mix of affects, materials, people, money and norms (Smith 2008) that expands from the house to the neighbourhood, locality, and even the country (Blunt & Dowling 2006). Assemblage-thinking offers one novel way of linking these various scales and elements of a home, being a particularly valuable theoretical lens when 'homemaking' concerns two unconnected individuals, tenant and landlord. Commonly, assemblage theories are mobilised at the large

scale of the global, region, the city and only recently have they been applied to home. To understand the ways in which private tenants assemble a fragile sense of home in the market-based PRS of the UK, the concept of ‘home-assembling’ (Soaita & McKee 2019) distinguishes their constrained practices and reduced control from the traditional concept of ‘homemaking’ (Easthome 2004) and from the new one of ‘home-unmaking’ (when homes are destroyed by wars, regeneration, domestic abuse; e.g. Harris et al. 2020). However, the privately-rented home is assembled within very different articulations of the state/market/culture nexus. Zooming in just in Europe, we find that the insecure, market-based rental arrangements in the UK hinder home-making as oppose to the supportive rental regimes of much of the continental Europe, while the PC world remains unexplored territory, against which assemblage concepts can be expanded and enriched.

While assemblage-thinking informs this proposal, its ambition is to feed back two specific conceptual advances. This proposal will reconsider the spatial concepts of (de)/(re)-territorialisation/stabilisation (DeLanda 2016) as they are particularly useful in understanding the processes, affects and materialities through which a sense of home is made, unmade or remade within and between tenancies (Soaita & McKee 2019). They are, however, incomplete for understanding the relationship of home with its physical space (e.g. this house, neighbourhood), its subjective space (e.g. this space of belonging or alienation) and its abstract space (i.e. one’s idea of the desired home). Understanding how a home’s physical, subjective and abstract spaces are (des)/(re)-assembled is not just an academic quest for conceptual clarity but important for tenants’ wellbeing because much policy emphasis is directly to physical instability (i.e. eviction or forced relocation), disregarding tenants’ subjective space according to which a home is lived in, and landlords’ abstract space according to which a privately rented property is put on the market.

Assemblage-thinking emphasises the temporal aspect of ‘becoming’ (Buchanan & Lambert 2005), which is important to understand the formation of tenants’ sense of home and the social relations in emerging PRS, more broadly. This proposal will use rhythmanalysis (Lefebvre 2004) to develop the concept of home’s rhythms, as a more granular view of everyday lived-time than the housing temporal concepts of life history, lifecycle, life course or pathway (Clapham 2002, Marcus 2006). As a way of thinking and a method, rhythmanalysis delineates between different types of time (e.g. linear of the clock; cyclical of nature) along which our sense of home unfolds in the everyday, in harmony or distress. Being alert to the multiple, intersecting rhythms of home-assembling builds a richer understanding of questions of (im)mobility, ill/wellbeing, place-making. Rhythmanalysis has not yet informed housing or assemblage studies although it has become more popular since 2014 in studies of migration, tourism and transport (a search in SCOPUS identified 162 studies, of which only two focused on housing). While Lefebvre saw researcher’s reflection as the way to conduct rhythmanalysis, I propose a research/participant co-production approach through a process of explanation, reflection and discussion (Marcu 2017).

1.1.3 Objectives (O) and research questions (RQ)

O1: To understand, through the concept of home as assemblage, the affective economies of emerging and hidden PRS based on existing international evidence and in-depth, bespoke insights from Romania:

RQ1: Why do tenants and landlords engage in the PRS?

RQ2: What are their affective and material practices of constructing a sense of home in a privately rented property?

RQ3: How do they construct ideas of power, risk and trust when navigating market transactions, state regulations and cultural understandings?

O2: To make conceptual advances by nuancing existing concepts of space and proposing new concepts of time

RQ4: In which ways do tenants’ and landlords’ practices territorialise/stabilise the sense of home within and between tenancies and how do these practices relate to home’s physical, subjective and abstract space?

RQ5: To what extent could the lived time of home and home-assembling be understood through rhythmanalysis?

O3: To imagine a sustainable and fair PRS in Romania and inform the national debate on its regulation

RQ6: What are the societal and policy implications of private tenants’ and landlords’ practices for a sustainable and fair PRS in face of increasing economic inequality, ageing and depopulation?

A carefully thought through and targeted inter-disciplinary approach, sequenced to create synergies across the project’s work packages guarantees that RQ are realistically achievable. A comprehensive set of deliverables, milestones and open-science practice ensures objectives are measurable and verifiable.

1.1.4 The Romanian case-study

Clearly, housing conditions in Romania have improved in the last decade, but they have done so unequally across the income spectrum. In fact, housing inequalities have increased between the bottom 40% and the rest of the population and between those owning multiple properties and those increasingly renting privately (Soaita and Dewilde 2019, 2020).

While official data show that just 1.3% of people rent privately, scholars (e.g. Hegedüs et al. 2018) estimated that at least 10% do so informally, positioning the country as an excellent case-study to examine the challenges and opportunities that an emerging and hidden PRS poses to both tenants and landlords. Indeed, the media mushrooms with advice to tenants and landlords while letting agencies advertise expensive, good quality, furnished homes for rent, targeted at better off tenants. However, below this affluent rental market, hidden and precarious practices have developed among the less affluent (Lancione 2019; Zamfirescu & Chelcea 2020), with many families being forced or having no other choice but to (sub)rent privately, notwithstanding costs and conditions. These observations suggest that the Romanian emerging, largely hidden PRS accommodates huge socioeconomic inequalities and vulnerabilities.

While the market seems to serve well some better off tenants (e.g. because advertised properties are not snapped up fast and are of good quality), the regulatory landscape does not. The PRS is only very lightly regulated by the Housing Act 114/1996 and the Civil Code 2020 (9 articles out of 2,664). Despite low levels of landlord taxation (tax of 10% applied on 60% of the rent), these small legal protections are sidestepped through dominant informal practices, putting at risk both marginal tenants and landlords. Romania offers therefore an excellent social laboratory to examine the social relations that frame an emerging and hidden PRS.

1.2 Soundness of the proposed methodology

The proposal brings a unique comparative focus on tenants and landlords across all the work packages (WP), which is theoretically required since home is materially and affectively co-assembled by both parties. To achieve conceptual depth, it combines novel approaches developed from meta-ethnography (WP1), sociology (WP2), visual studies (WP2,3) and public policy (WP4) to carefully address its RQ and grasp the multi-scalar and multi-dimensionality of home. Each WP will offer a standalone conceptual contribution, expanding methodological innovations in their fields, while their sequencing within the project facilitates integration and strategic synergies to answer the O and enhance the potential for impact.

O	RQ	WP	Method
O1	1, 2, 3	WP1	A critical interpretative synthesis (CIS) of existing qualitative evidence
		WP2	Qualitative questionnaire: WP2a (online for digitally savvy) & WP2b (with digitally excluded)
O2	4, 5	WP3	Photo-elicitation interviews, also referred to as visual ethnography (Barratt and Green 2017)
O3	6	WP4	Scenario building: co-creation workshop

WP1: CIS will address the international component of O1 by systematically examining tenants' and landlords' motivations and practices in countries of high economic informality (mostly those outside AS-c and Western Europe), with attention to unpack the market/state/culture nexus within their PRS. CIS is a novel approach to reviewing (Depraetere et al. 2020), aimed at developing theory rather than just aggregating existing evidence. Building on a more feasible approach and prior experience (Soaita et al. 2019; 2021), the literature will be retrieved through systematic bibliographical searches (SCOPUS and Web of Science) using a set of relevant keywords that describe the population and phenomenon of interest and research design. Following best practice and clear protocol, analysis will start by reducing the retrieved literature to most relevant studies. Data will be then extracted by categories (e.g. country; RQ; theory; context; method; findings) and analysed thematically (with NVivo software). A research output in its own right, it will also contextualise WP2 findings and inform WP4.

WP2: The rarely used method of a qualitative questionnaire, which collects excellent data of breadth and depth (Soaita 2021), will address O1 by bringing bespoke evidence from Romania (routed separately for tenant and landlords). To deliver geographical nuance, it will be delivered online (WP2a), with promotion in sampled cities' Facebook groups and tenants/landlords sites. Besides some closed-ended questions, about 10 open-ended ones will ask about: reasons for renting/letting; addressing risks; building trust; making home. Participants will be invited to email photographs of the rented property (with comments) and subscribe for participation in WP3. Data will be analysed thematically (counted/cross-tabulated whenever relevant), first separately by group, then comparatively. The issue of digital exclusion is addressed in WP2b by face-to-face delivery in three nearby cities: Bucharest (large), Pitesti (medium) and Calarasi (small) where a few interviews with Roma people will be conducted. These conversations will cover a structured part similar to WP2a and a photo-elicitation part similar to WP3.

WP3: The specific conceptual contributions (O2) will be advanced through a suitably large sample of online photo-elicitation interviews, in conjunction with WP1 and WP2 data. Adding deeper insights to WP2 data, elicitation on participant-supplied photographs is particularly useful in the study of home given the importance of materiality to the

expression of self and wellbeing (Soaita & McKee 2020). Tenants will be required to send and discuss photos that reflect spatial and temporal concepts (e.g. something that makes/stops you feel at home; an ordinary/out of ordinary activity). Landlords will be requested to send and discuss the advertising photos of their property. These in-depth discussions (and further probes) will flesh out the process of home-assembling in/through space and time. Interviewees, invited through WP2, will be selected to cover a diversity of participant characteristics; analysis will be theoretically informed. Given PRS informality, the approach of dyads tenant/landlord was dismissed on ethical grounds.

WP4: To address O3, the ‘scenario building’ method aims to debate the future of the PRS in Romania and co-produce a ‘Guide for Good Practice’. Informed by a few expert interviews and by WP1,2,3 findings, a 3-hour workshop will bring together relevant stakeholders (tenants, landlords, letting-agents, public officers, civil society), opening channels to influence policymaking beyond the life of the study.

Diversity & gender: The characteristics of the tenant and landlord population are unknown, but care will be given to observe diversity variables (gender, age, ethnicity, migration status) within WP1 synthesis, through WP2 targeted promotion (incl. Roma population), WP3 purposeful sampling, and in WP4 workshop. While women are over represented through self-selection in qualitative questionnaires (Soaita 2021), this is not problematic as poor renting experiences are associated with both low income and being a female (particularly single, single mother and elderly). Care will be taken to include all ages because Romania is depicted as an ageist society (Iossifova 2020). Diversity characteristics will be reflected upon during conceptualisation, data collection, analysis, and dissemination.

Open science: *Mandatory practices:* Three peer-reviewed journal articles will be Open Access, and additionally widely shared to the academic community (e.g. through Research.Gate and Zenedo). Data will be responsibly made FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable). The principle of ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’, will be interpreted as follows: anonymised research data will be made FAIR based on participants’ consent, asked separately for text (whether imputed in questionnaire or transcript) and image (photographs); all audio or video recordings will be deleted after transcription, except those used for video snippets in dissemination (while this is not research data, full informed consent will be asked). FAIR data will be stored in the EOSC (of which the host university is signatory) and/or Zenodo with an embargo access of two years after the end of the project (to allow time for more publications). However, information required to validate the results/conclusions reported in the scientific publications will be offered in a confidential manner if needed besides open access data protocols shared early. *Recommended practices:* Early information to validate or replicate results will be offered in the form of a Briefing Protocol for WP1 (Boolean strings used in literature searches; inclusion/exclusion criteria used to select the most relevant literature for reviewing and diagrammatic or tabular process visualisation; coding framework for data extraction; and map of key themes) and a Briefing Protocol for WP2 (the full questionnaire structure). The project and the briefing papers will be preregistered in Zenedo and/or OSF, and accessible from the project digital platforms. The project includes a *co-creation* element in the form of a workshop with a range of stakeholders to co-produce a narrative for the best policy-path towards a fair PRS and a ‘Guide for Good Practice’, with an element of co-assessment (see section 3).

Ethics and research data management plan (DMP): Ethics approval will be sought from the host University of Bucharest (UB), Romania (submitted month 2); see a detailed description in Form A for WP2,3,4 and B-1 for more information related to communication actions. The project is low-risk. My 4-years’ service in the University of Glasgow Ethics Committee guarantees that best practice will be adhered to at all times, from the design of participant info packs, to maintaining confidentiality & anonymity, and further to reporting, data storage & archival, personal data processing, including waving of intellectual property rights for text and images. A DMP for the lifecycle of the research will be delivered in month 6 (on the Commission template), detailing through protocol how the data set is described, uniquely identified, guarded and curated, and under what conditions it can be accessed during the life of the project and afterwards. The DMP will be developed with UB support, following Horizon recommended guidelines for good practice (e.g. CESSDA, Science Europe Practical Guide) and in the Annotated Grant Agreement.

1.3 Quality of the supervision, training & of the two-way transfer of knowledge

My supervisor, Prof Xxxxx Xxxxxxxx, teaches anthropology and sociology at the UB’s Department of Sociology (DoS) at the Faculty of Sociology and Social Work (FSSW), where he is Vice Dean. He has mentored three post-graduate researchers, supervised six PhD students and numerous master students. Two PhD dissertations dealt with renting in terms of evictions and homelessness in Bucharest; and a systematic review of all byelaws governing renting in Romania. Xxxxx sits in doctoral committees at Universities of California, Santa Cruz and Michigan (US), and Sheffield (UK). He is the head of the Ministry of Education’s committee that sets the standards for granting professorship and a member of

the Ministry of Research committee that sets the standards for research grant awards. He has been a referee for, e.g. European Research Council (ERC), Israel Science Foundation, Fulbright Commission, Romanian UEFISCDI, and for 20 top journals in urban studies, anthropology and geography.

Of relevance, Xxxxx's research focuses on housing, inequalities and infrastructures, and has earned international repute and collaborations (e.g. ERC HOUWEL on international housing market within a NL team; Marcinczak et al. 2014 on gentrification within a Scandinavian team). Xxxxx has focused on understanding time in the context of institutional transformation, proposing the concept of 'fantasy time' (Chelcea 2016) and 'zombie socialism' (Xxxxxxx & Druță 2016). Using assemblage-thinking, he examined infrastructure as assemblages, understanding movement over time/space through the concepts of 'flows' and 'connectivity' (Xxxxxxx & Pulay 2015) and through the 'rhythms of the city' in home-work mobility (Xxxxxxx & Iancu 2015). As an internationally trained anthropologist, Xxxxx is well placed to guide me to fluency in ethnographic approaches, which assemblage-studies cast as their preferred methods, and which will inform WP3 as a visual ethnography through photo-elicitation. Xxxxx will also ensure access to the hard-to-reach Roma participants in WP2b. As an indicator of our matching academic interests, we have met during conferences in Berlin, Amsterdam and over ZOOM; and we already collaborate as he sits on two of my projects' Advisory Boards.

Xxxxx and I have discussed my career goal of a tenured lectureship in Romania, my native country, by the end of this fellowship and fast progression to professorship (within the subsequent 5 years). Achieving my goals will also enable me to connect with my family (which Brexit has complicated). Xxxxx will be a central figure along my development path, mentoring me to navigate the Romanian academic system, where I have never worked before. We will have monthly meetings centred on transferable skills, e.g. networking and interaction (within academic committees and departments, funding bodies, publishers) and hands-on learning (teaching and research). We will identify positions of esteem for me to take (e.g. UB Research Ethics committee, of which Xxxxx is a member) to achieve my career goal in a timely manner. Importantly, we will prepare my application for Habilitation (*Abilitare*) in the 'Sociology of Housing' and 'Qualitative Research Methods' (end year1), which is a prerequisite to professorship. Xxxxx and the DoS will add a key sociological viewpoint to my housing expertise. We will review my career development plan, in order to access all the required support from the UB and its international networks.

Training will be carefully tailored to my career stage (7 years and 7 months) and goals. Since I have already undertaken significant research training, my key training objectives refer to career development (year 1&2), management & administration, and research funding (year1), teaching & learning (year2). The UB runs several **career development** modules, of which the most relevant for my goals is understanding indicators of academic excellence and the path to professorship (e.g. publications, research grants, positions of esteem). Together, we will identify training across UB (e.g. departmental MA in 'Human Resources Management') totaling at least 5 full days yearly. Mentoring will be essential. Besides Xxxxx's dedication, Prof Rodica Popescu (xxxxxx.xxxxxx@rei.ase.ro) of the Romanian Academy of Economic Studies, Bucharest, agreed to mentor me in navigating the path to lectureship and professorship status in Romania (we have co-authored one article and currently run a small, unfunded project together).

In terms of **management & admin**, I plan to attend at least 5 full days training on managing EU research funding, project budgeting, and managing a project portfolio and project team (year1). I already have the kind support of Ms Filuta Ionita and Mr Dragos Dena (contacts on this application) for a hands-on approach to ensure that the project runs smoothly. In addition, ex.Prof Dumitru Sandu, quantitative sociologist in DoS and Horizon2020 grant winner (649491/YMobility), agreed to mentor me on project management & administration, and help me navigate the UB, FSSW and DoS institutional and informal cultures (xxxxxx.xxxxx@gmail.com). Also in year 1, I will attend 3 full days training at UB's flagship Research Institute ICUB (where Xxxxx is Associate Member) on the **funding landscape** to increase my skills in securing high profile funding. The aim is to start developing a ERC grant application, capitalising on the synergies between my existing and expanded research network.

Although I have already engaged in **teaching & learning**, I need development in all aspects to achieve my career aim. In year 2, I will take 10 full-days related training, particularly relevant being UB's MA in 'Innovative Strategies of Learning' (offered by the FSSW department of Educational Sciences). In terms of learning-by-doing, I am keen to be involved in (post)graduate teaching, and student supervision on topics related to my expertise, similar to my current practice at the University of Glasgow (four lectures, three MA dissertations, yearly), hence I will contribute to the MA in Sociology Research (in English), and the Doctoral School of Sociology. I am excited to be offered the possibility to supervise Xxxxx's PhD students as I have never been allowed to do so in the UK given my short-term contracts. Finally, given that UB is part of CIVIS, an Erasmus+ European University Alliance, I will take advantage of

the CIVIS Academy's access to all relevant training offered across the other 8 member universities (where I am already registered through the University of Glasgow membership). Together, Xxxxx and I we will prepare a detailed Career Development Plan to be submitted in month 1.

Two-way knowledge transfer: I am a highly experienced researcher, and I can transfer my expertise in many ways. While peer-commenting on papers and/or co-authorship will be mutually helpful, my excellent English skills can much increase potential for article acceptance (I have peer-reviewed more than 80 manuscripts for 16 renowned international journals). While I have much to learn/gain from engagement in teaching, this will also facilitate transfer of my expertise on a range of theoretical, methodological and empirical subjects; my engagement will make a key input to the Sociology programme, which is taught in English, and to DoS aim to internationalise its curricula (within the project time allocation). While I am interested to learn about ethnographic approaches, I will contribute two half-day training, yearly (e.g. photo-elicitation; systematic literature searching; remote research methods, NVivo) to staff & students. To increase potential for grant winning, cross-fertilising my international network (AUS, GBR, NLD) with those in DoS & ICUB (FIN, ITA, USA) will benefit all parties. In particular, I can facilitate for my colleagues to present at (online) workshops/seminars in the UK (e.g. Glasgow and York) and co-convene sessions at international conferences. Moreover, DoS & UB profiles will gain visibility as MSCA host institutions through project activities/outputs, having the opportunity to consolidate their managing experience with EU funded projects, while offering support for project actions (e.g. free venues, hosting arrangements). In the same time, I learn related management & communication skills.

1.4 Researcher's professional experience, competences and skills

This ambitious project builds on my academic experience of 7 years and 7 months, acquired across three renowned universities. I have used various theories and concepts across my work (e.g. Deleuze's 'the fold', Esping-Anderson's regime theory, Polanyi's tacit-knowing, Lakoff's 'metaphors we go by', Lefebvre's Right to the City), but I have recently become captivated by the possibilities offered by assemblage theories. While I have so far engaged in an empirically steered approach (Soaita & McKee 2019), this proposal is theoretically instilled by assemblage thinking, aiming to make specific conceptual contributions on questions of time and space. Methodologically, I have engaged with traditional and more creative qualitative & quantitative methods across many projects (proficiency in NVivo and SPSS). Of relevance to this proposal, I lead on 'literature mapping' and conducted a critical interpretative synthesis (Soaita et al. 2019, 2021); have used qualitative questionnaires with excellent results (Soaita 2021); and engaged with remote photo-elicitation interviews (Soaita and McKee 2020). WP4 co-creation approach draws on experience in hosting workshops with a variety of stakeholders at my current employment. Substantively, I am a growing expert in UK and Romanian housing. I have knowledge related to PRS, particularly in AS-c but also in the Indian subcontinent (CI in a current project). I have conducted primary research with private tenants, tenant activists and landlords in the UK; led one international review on tenants' experiences in AS-c and another on housing wealth inequalities in OECD countries. Overall, I have worked and published on a range of key housing topics related to policy, inequalities and home (21 journal articles, 20 reports/working papers). My achievements were recognised with a promotion from grade 7 (Associate) to 8 (Fellow) in 2020. Given my interdisciplinary background (urban and housing studies, human geography, sociology, architecture & planning), I am able to create interdisciplinary synergies within this project.

2. IMPACT

2.1 Measures to enhance my career perspectives & employability, and skills development

My career goal is to obtain a tenured lectureship by the end of MSCA and progress to professorship within the next 5 years in Romania. After having acquired extensive specialist knowledge through 15 years of international education and employment in competitive academic settings, I want to transfer my knowledge to the Romanian academia, to nurture and inspire Romanian students. Towards this goal, my stay at UB will give me the opportunity to learn an essential skill: converting into Romanian (mother tongue) the academic knowledge that I have acquired exclusively in English. Through mentoring and training, I will also develop the communication skills for navigating the Romanian academic environment, understanding the career-path to professorship, and learning to strategically target the 21 indicators of excellence that would take me there. While my publication profile is highly competitive, it is not currently matched by the necessary teaching & learning skills, which MSCA will give me the opportunity to develop through hands-on action, mentoring and training. My full affiliation with the DoS will ensure obtaining Habilitation in two subjects by the end of year 1. MSCA will strengthen my competitive profile with the opportunity to gain the management and admin skills of running an important project as a Principle Investigator in DoS and UB where I aim to achieve my tenured lectureship position. The project co-creation and communication actions will develop the soft skills required in effective public

engagement with non-academic stakeholders while Xxxxx's and my mentors' dedication will support the development of communication skills and networking with the near-academia environment, e.g. publishers. While these actions will enable me to settle in the Romanian academia, MSCA project and the very prestige of the Fellowship will be essential for enhancing my international academic profile through ambitious publications in top journals: they will reinforce my leadership in assemblage theory in international housing studies. Towards these career development goals of strengthening my competitiveness in the Romanian academia and increasing my international standing, developing new grant applications is fundamental. MSCA will offer opportunities to enhance my communication and networking skills to develop an interdisciplinary grant application through collaborations within the UB, and UB & DoS international networks. New methodological skills (e.g. ethnographic approaches and working with hard-to-reach participants) and the crafting skills for grant applications, strengthened through planned training, will increase potential for success.

2.2 Measures to maximize expected outcomes and impacts

As the PRS generates important inequalities of wealth and wellbeing, it is important to maximize the project impact. A detailed Dissemination and Exploitation plan will be provided if funded. This is summarised below.

Disseminating findings to other research settings promotes the theoretical relevance of this study, adding value to the project in at least three ways: strengthening work-in-progress, raising the project profile and increase potential for future collaboration. I propose three open access journal articles, and in-person presentations to two international conferences and two national workshops. Journal article submissions will be made to *Housing Studies* (“Understanding the market/state/culture nexus of hidden PRS: a critical interpretative synthesis of international qualitative literature”); *Geoforum* (“The micro-politics of materiality, territory and affect in emerging PRS”); *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers* (“The rhythms of a temporarily home”). I have published in the first two journals and peer reviewed for all three.

Conference presentations will be made in-person at the annual conferences of *Royal Geographical Society* and the *European Network for Housing Researchers*. At the former, I will launch a call for an online theoretical session on Lefebvrian-inspired research (as I did on Bourdieu in 2021; the latter has set workshops only). National workshops, to be attended in person, will be organised at Babes-Bolyai University and at the University of Iasi, where my supervisor already has contacts. These two nationally renowned universities were selected for both disseminating findings and expanding my national network, which is currently internationally biased. Additionally, toward the end of the project, I will organise one online international seminar (call: “The post-Covid social world of hidden PRS across the globe”).

Not shown in the Gantt Chart: taking advantage of my/host international network, I will pro-actively present as invited guest work-in-progress and findings at about two international seminars, yearly (mostly online) at universities renowned for their housing research (e.g. Glasgow; Tilburg; Dublin; other CIVIS universities). I will also write two blogs for international venues (e.g. UK Collaborative Centre for Housing Evidence: “Lessons to learn from abroad: tenants and landlords in Romania”; The Conversation: “Five things we learned increase trust between tenants and landlords in untrusting markets”). In addition, the project will be promoted and listed on a range of different platforms (e.g. Research Gate and CORDIS) and presented through CIVIS Academy.

Communicating research progress and findings to the general public will involve press releases for launch & end events (by UB media office) and active project-related information through its website, YouTube (I am a learned uploader), Facebook and Twitter channels. News (including the briefings), guests' and own podcasts, and three video snippets (e.g. street opinions on what means: a good tenant; a good landlord; a good rented home) will be regularly posted. *Not in the Gantt Chart:* to stir public debate, WP2,3 findings will be journalistically synthesised in two press articles (national coverage in *Adevarul* and *Gandul*), one aimed at critiquing prejudice and discrimination in the PRS, the other on ways to increase trust between tenants and landlords. To reach tenants, landlords and agents, the ‘Guide for Good Practice’ (checklist) will be communicated through two blogs in real estate platforms (e.g. *SpatiuConstruct.Ro*; *Imobiliare.Ro*). As WP2a digital recruitment will use Facebook groups, results will be posted back (the four briefing papers on findings). Targeted audiences will be engaged in the three project workshops where every effort will be made to reach policymakers, particularly though their analysts and policy teams as invited stakeholders (opening thus one road to exploitation).

Exploitation of results will directly be implemented through research-led teaching during and after the project end, and through the development of a large, collaborative grant application (e.g. ERC grant, first year after MSCA end), towards which the international dissemination strategies are targeted. Furthermore, the project aims to raise awareness of good practice in the PRS, and will ideally steer cultural change among all actors involved, giving direction

and inspiration through its ‘Guide for Good Practice’, which I will continue to promote after MSCA end, digitally, through the project network, and handed out in future events.

2.3. The magnitude & importance of the project’s contribution to expected scientific, societal and economic impacts

This proposal aims to open up the academic debate along three directions. First, it will introduce assemblage-thinking to housing studies, which can benefit from a re-engagement with the materiality and affects of ‘home/housing’ while helping to bring together its chains of production and consumption in more relational, non-essentialized and explicit ways. Second, this project proposes to both assemblage and housing studies a yet little explored way of understanding the non-linear dimensions of lived space and time, i.e. rhythmanalysis. In its quest to substantiate the concept of home’s rhythms, it will take the unusual approach of reflective co-creation between participant and researcher rather than basing it exclusively on researcher self-reflection (as conceived by Lefebvre). Finally, this research produces new knowledge through its empirical engagement with the hidden PRS, globally and in the PC context. This will help redirect the research gaze away from dominant Anglo-Saxon viewpoints and shed light on more ‘hidden’ and unexplored social worlds.

Through its element of defining and communicating good practice in the Romanian PRS, the proposal aims to prompt social impact. It is hoped the project will raise landlords’ awareness on what is needed for a rented property to become a tenant’s home, and will help tenants frame their claim to home. The vital importance of a good home to tenants’ wellbeing has been evidenced by prior research and has become conspicuous during the Covid-19 pandemic. It was shown that just casting tenants’ plight as a matter of public concern gives tenants a sense of wellbeing. It is hoped to also raise public/policymakers’ awareness of the importance of a sustainable and fair PRS. In terms of magnitude of the impact, 126-189 participants will be influenced through self-reflection during the research process; 90 stakeholders through workshops; and many more will be reached through the project’s active and diverse communication actions. By helping construct a shared understanding of good practice in the PRS, the project could theoretically improve the lives of many private tenants, whether the officially registered 252,000 or the over one million estimated.

3. IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Quality & effectiveness of the WP, risk assessment and effort assigned

The four research WPs plus a transversal **WP5 (training, impact & admin)** are mapped in the Gantt Chart below and described after that. The effort assigned was carefully calculated and indicated based on a full-time year of 1,840 hours (h), i.e. 153h=1 person-month (p-m), after excluding statutory leave.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	
WP1: 628h=4.1 p-m	a	a	a	a	a	w	w						v	v											
WP2a: 665h=4.3 p-m		p	r	r	r	r	r	r	r	r	ra	ra	a	w	w									v	v
WP2b: 144h=0.9 p-m						r	r	r	r	r	r	r	a	w	w										
WP3: 901h=5.9 p-m						r	r	r	r	r	r	r	ra	ra	a	a	a	a	a	w	w	w			
WP4: 278h=1.8 p-m																			p	p	a	a	w	w	
WP5: 736h=4.8 p-m																									
Deliverables																									
<i>Mobility decl. & CDP (12h)</i>	x																								
<i>Web/YouTube/FB/Twitter (24h)</i>	x																								
<i>Ethics & Advisory Board (24h)</i>		x																							
<i>Launch & End works. (0.8 p-m)</i>			x																					x	
<i>6 briefing papers</i>			x	x			x								x								x		x
<i>DMP & Diss. Plan (12h)</i>						x																			
<i>3 articles submission</i>							x								x								x		
<i>Co-creation workshop</i>																						x			
<i>Online international seminar</i>																		x							
<i>Conf. & works. (128h/0.8 p-m)</i>						x								x						x	x				
<i>Plan exploitation of results</i>																								x	

Legend for shown activities: a=analysis; p=preparation; r=recruitment/promotion; v=revision; w=writing up; x =milestone. When time loads not shown, the activity is included in a WP load.

WP1: month (m.) 1-7 (milestones). Conducting CIS of existing literature. *Deliverables:* 1st briefing (m.3, on protocol); 2nd briefing (m.7, on finding), 1st article submission (m.7). *Risk mitigation:* to make the work feasible and depending on the size of the literature, inclusion/exclusion criteria will be set (e.g. publishing timeline, selected countries).

WP2a: m.2-15 (milestones). Designing in QuestionPro and piloting the online qualitative questionnaire: m.2; Launching & promoting until 80 submissions from each group are reached (minimum 50 for each): m.3-10(or12); Analysis and writing up m.10(or12)-15. *Deliverables*: 3rd briefing (m.4, on protocol), 4th briefing (m.15, findings), 2nd article submission (m.15.). *Risk mitigation*: to mitigate expected low-response rate, the method requires prolonged promotion (Soaita 2021), hence the surveys will be open for up to 8 months (m.3-10) but extended to m.12 if needed. This will also help mitigate the risk of biased self-selection (e.g. geographically, age, gender) through targeted promotion. As the characteristics of the two populations of interest are unknown, the sample will be examined and fine-tuned with ongoing submissions in order to obtain broad national coverage.

WP2b: m.6-15 (milestones). Recruit & conduct 6-9 interviews with Roma people (90 min) any time between m.6-12; analysis m.12-15. *Deliverables*: as data complement and fit into WP2 and WP3, there are no separate outputs. *Risk mitigation*: to stimulate participation, a €40 Thank You voucher will be offered to these disadvantaged participants.

WP3: m.6-22 (milestones). Recruit & conduct 25-40 online photo-elicitation interviews (tenant/landlord split roughly 50:50; about 60 min each). Preliminary analysis conducted concomitantly with recruitment over m.6-12; analysis m.13-22. *Deliverables*: 5th briefing (m.22), 3rd article submission (m.22). *Risk mitigation*: to stimulate participation, a €20 Thank You voucher will be offered; WP3 can be extended to m.14 if take up is slow; if not enough participants subscribe via WP2 or the sample is biased, snowballing recruitment will be sought in the same three cities of WP2b.

WP4: m.19-24 (milestones). Workshop preparation (m.19-20): analysis of the few Romanian housing policy documents; 5 expert interviews (€20 voucher); WP1,2,3 findings will be synthesised in the form of ‘persona briefing’, i.e. imaginary tenants, and their ‘fate’ in some of the WP1’s selected countries and Romania (e.g. a low-income minority-ethnic family, a single mother); Obtain venue, recruit stakeholders (m.20); prepare small information pack to be handed out prior to the day; prepare Power Point presentation to be delivered on the day; organise hospitality; Workshop (m.21) with brainstorming sessions organized across 5-6 round-tables (framed by questions around the persona’s housing challenges, the future and best practice); Follow-up output for co-assessment (m.23). *Deliverables*: workshop (m.21), 6th briefing (m.24, Guide for Good Practice). *Risk mitigation*: if discussions are inconclusive, a follow-up questionnaire (m.22) will be emailed to each participant for clarification.

Transversal WP5: m.1-24. *Impact*: project website, YouTube, Facebook and Twitter accounts (m.1) and regular posting; internal DoS seminar presentation (m.2); Advisory Board (m.2); Launch event (m.3); online international seminar convenor (m.18); End event (m.23). *No milestones*: 2 in-person international conferences (about m.14 and m.21); 2 in-person national workshops (about m.6 and m.20); 2 online international seminars; 2 international and 2 national blogs, 2 newspaper articles (one of each yearly); *Training*: attending 13 days year1 and 15 days year2; giving two half-day training (one yearly), plus hands-on learning related to teaching, student supervision, management & admin. *Career development*: Habilitation submitted (m.12); all professorship criteria met (m.24). *Others*: Ethics (m.1); monthly meeting with supervisor, bi-monthly meeting with mentors. *Risk mitigation*: If other academic duties endanger research delivery, research prioritisation will be discussed with the supervisor, teaching/learning activities will be reduced and admin support increased. Covid-19 restrictions will be carefully accommodated, e.g. WP2b can be conducted via telephone, WP4 online and conference/workshop presentations given exclusively online. However, the three project workshops are preferred to be delivered in-person.

Indicative research budget: Vouchers (€840- €1,260); transcription (€2,600-€3,900 at €1.1/min); four WP2 fieldwork visits (€150x4); NVivo user license (€2,000); three Open Access articles (€2,300x3); two international conferences (€1,500x2); two national workshops (€400x2); three project workshops (€1200x3; each includes attendees’ bursaries and hospitality; venue free); consumables (€2,000). **Total costs**: €22,300 to €24,000 (rounded).

3.2 Quality & capacity of the host institution, including hosting arrangements

Founded in 1864, UB is the first Romanian institution to reach the top 600 universities in the QS World University Ranking. It offers a vibrant research environment, having collaborations with over 100 prestigious universities from 40 countries, including CIVIS network. The university flagship Research Institute ICUB (where my supervisor holds associate membership), promotes outstanding interdisciplinary research and opens its capacity to all UB staff, encouraging international/interdisciplinary projects, organising workshops, conferences and training. One of UB’s 19 faculties, FSSW hosts four departments, 57 Professors; 2,500 students (120 PhD); 14 master programmes; 11 research centres; and four laboratories. Its space doubled recently though a building extension. Several of UB’s European funded projects were hosted in FSSW (e.g. FP6 CESSDA; PPP/FP7 *Data without Boundaries*, FP7 EUCROSS). Its DoS (formed in 1910) provides excellent research and research-based education (some in English, to which I will contribute).

Its multi/inter-disciplinary programmes centred on social policies and stratification, anthropology, housing and cities, crime, institutional change. It runs its own research seminar with internal and external presenters. In the past decade DoS has produced studies published in top international journals, in areas such as survey design, ethnographic and field methods, housing, emotions, gender, cities, informality. DoS hosted (and continue to invite) reputable visiting academics, e.g. Michael Burawoy, ex-president of the American Sociological Association, Katherine Verdery, distinguished professor at the City University of New York, Michele Lancione, Universities of Sheffield/Torino, Erica van der Sijpt, University of Amsterdam, Stephen Cutler, University of Vermont.

DoS both matches and complements my theoretical expertise and I am looking forwards to new learning and collaborations. Of relevance to my project, Prof Jderu published intensely in the sociology of emotions; DoS has a rich expertise in the sociology and anthropology of economic behavior and informality (e.g. Baltasiu, Chelcea, Craciun), the sociology of risk (Urse), time (Matei) and routine (Poenaru). Besides knowing Xxxx, I have occasionally met other DoS staff (e.g. Righinis, Sava), which will ensure my swift integration. I will join the research centre of ‘Geopolitics and social anthropology’, one of the 11 FSSW research centres. I will be active in DoS seminars and its informal culture (collective lunch; Friday drinks). On arrival, I will present my research profile at the DoS seminar (invitation across UoB) to speed up integration and raise the potential for mutually beneficial collaborations in grants and papers.

For the efficient fulfillment of this action in all its aspects, the Host will provide: Supervision and mentoring; All necessary practical arrangements (e.g. generous office space, access to internet and library); Research software (Mendeley; QuestionPro); Opportunities for academic multidisciplinary engagement within FSSW, ICUB, UB but also nationally and internationally; Admin support for travelling arrangements (e.g. for fieldwork, conferences, workshops, incl. Quartz admin platform); Free UB venue for the three workshops; Support for European/national press coverage for the project; Opportunities to undertake teaching & learning activities; Access to all UB career development programmes, training modules; One-to-one advice and annual personal development reviews; Numerous activities and initiatives organised at UB international network level, facilitating training, networking, collaborative grant applications. The overall management of the project will lie with UB, which has robust procedures and policies for efficient and appropriate administration of similar projects, and with whom I will collaborate closely (e.g. departments for Research Management, International Relations and Human Resources). UB will provide me with one-on-one support on project management & implementation, research contracts and grant agreements as will my supervisor and mentor (former PI in YMobility Prof Dumitru).

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